

Mysterious Card Box: Analysis of Creative Thinking Skills in Elementary School Thematic Learning

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ABSTRACT: The use of media in learning is very urgent. Thematic learning students are required to have the ability to think creatively and complexly. This study aims to determine the use of media in thematic learning to foster students' creative thinking skills. This study used a qualitative descriptive method which was conducted in three schools involving teachers and fifth grade elementary school students as respondents. Data collection instruments used questionnaires, interviews and observations by providing questions and questionnaires regarding the use of media in thematic learning. The results of data analysis in this study indicate that the lack of use of media in thematic learning. Learners can cultivate creative thinking skills by using alternative media in learning. Mysterious card box media is one of the media that can be used to foster students' creative thinking skills in thematic learning.

KEYWORDS: Creative Thinking and Thematic, Elementary School, Media, Learning, Mysterious Card Box.

INTRODUCTION

Learning media is a tool or intermediary that is useful for facilitating the teaching and learning process, in order to streamline communication between teachers and students. This is very helpful for teachers in teaching and makes it easier for students to receive and understand lessons. This process requires teachers who are able to align between learning media and learning methods. According to Faturrahman et al (2021) learning media is anything that can attract students' attention and interest when learning, so that students become more curious about understanding lessons.

The use of learning media in the teaching and learning process can also generate new desires and interests for students, generate motivation to learn, and even have a psychological influence on students. Besides being able to increase student learning motivation, the use or use of media can also increase students' understanding of the lesson. Media has a very important meaning in learning because the media can generate new desires and interests, generate motivation and stimulate learning activities and even bring psychological influences on students (Rusiana, 2014). The learning process with the help of learning media will increase optimal cognitive learning outcomes (Nuralisa et al., 2021).

Wiana (2018) states that "Learning media used today is more diverse, ranging from conventional media such as books or traditional props to modern audio-visual media such as cassettes, videos, and other modern performances. Learning media is used to facilitate communication in teaching and learning processes, strived optimally to be able to foster creativity and motivation in learning activities to improve the quality of education. One of the media used in learning and believed to be more exciting student interest in the lecture is an interactive learning media based on animation. The statement stated that the learning media used today are more diverse, ranging from conventional media such as books or traditional teaching aids to modern audio-visual media such as cassettes, videos, and other modern ones. Learning media used to facilitate communication in the teaching and learning process are optimally pursued to be able to foster creativity and motivation in learning activities to improve the quality of education.

The ability to think, both critical and creative thinking is very important in the field of education today. This is evident from various government efforts in making policies in the field of education which include these two components in various educational activities, both contained in the curriculum, learning strategies and other learning tools (Mardiyanti, 2020). Education standards in the 21st century that students have the ability to think creatively in solving problems (Alfiyah et al., 2023). According to Hartadiyati et al (2015) The ability to think creatively is a very essential ability for life, work, and to function effectively in all other aspects of life.

Creative thinking skills are not an instant learning result that can be measured by two to three times the test is then declared good or not (Jeet & Pant, 2023). According to Cetinkaya (2014) "The most extensive definition about creativity with regard to gifted skills" this statement explains that creativity is closely related to gifted skills.

The rapid development of science and technology emphasizes a person to be able to improve self-quality. The learning process that is applied must be a place for students to develop their thinking skills (Siswanto & Ratiningsih, 2020). In line with this opinion, Permana (2018) argues that creative thinking is needed to generate alternative problem solving, creative thinking as a combination of logical thinking and divergent thinking based on intuition but still in awareness. When someone applies creative thinking in a problem solving practice, divergent thinking produces many useful ideas in solving problems. According to Suryandari et al (2021) Creative thinking is the ability to generate many ideas as mental challenges. The statement explains that creative thinking is the ability to produce many ideas that can be developed.

Thematic learning is a form of integrated learning that links some material and basic competencies to several subjects that are integrated into one particular theme by enabling students to learn, both individually and in groups, to actively explore and discover scientific concepts and principles in a holistic and meaningful way. . This is in line with Rusman (2012) who argues that thematic learning is one of the integrated learning models (integrated instruction) which is a learning system that allows students both individually and in groups to actively explore and discover scientific concepts and principles in a holistic, meaningful way. and authentic. Thematic learning is a form or model of integrated learning, namely the netted model (webbeb), which basically emphasizes integrated organizational patterns combined with a theme. Themes are taken and developed from outside the subject but in line with basic competencies and topics from the subject (Kurniawan, 2017). Regarding thematic learning, Rahmawati et al (2021) explained that integrated thematic learning is learning that combines or integrates material from several subjects into one harmonious theme. Learning. The choice of thematic as the scope because in elementary school thematic has the longest portion of time compared to other subjects (Fauzi et al., 2021).

In research conducted by Russiana (2014) the use of KOKAMI media (mysterious card boxes) in thematic learning was able to increase listening activities, discussion activities and was able to improve learning outcomes for fifth grade elementary school students. In line with research conducted by Faturrahman et al (2021) that the KOKAMI media (mysterious card box) meets the eligibility category for use in thematic learning. Media is very influential in the learning process. One of them is the use of KOKAMI media (mysterious card box). KOKAMI media (mysterious card box) has the advantage of learning combined with games, using message cards and envelopes that are designed to vary according to the activities needed. In research conducted by Widodo & Suprayitno (2017) KOKAMI media (mysterious card box) has a significant influence on learning outcomes in the realm of knowledge, understanding and application.

Based on the explanation above, the research conducted can be used as a basis for developing a learning media in the form of a mystery card box (KOKAMI). Seeing how important the use of media is in thematic learning, this is an important influence for teachers in improving the learning process and students' thinking power. The purpose of this study is to identify and describe the use of KOKAMI media (mysterious card box) in thematic learning to foster students' creative thinking skills. analyze and describe students' creative thinking skills in thematic learning using KOKAMI media (mysterious card box). Based on the background and previous research that has been elaborated on above, it is necessary to conduct research entitled KOKAMI media (mysterious card box): analysis of creative thinking skills in thematic learning of students at SD Negeri 1 Sumberagung Metro Kibang, East Lampung.

METHODS

This study uses a qualitative descriptive method, data collection techniques used are questionnaires, interviews and observation. This research was conducted on fifth grade students of Public Elementary School 1 Sumberagung, Public Elementary School 2 Sumberagung and Public Elementary School 2 Margototo Metro Kibang East Lampung with a total of 59 students. Data collection using a questionnaire is used to analyze the needs of students regarding the use of media in thematic learning. Interviews were conducted with fifth grade teachers at Public Elementary School 1 Sumberagung, Public Elementary School 2 Sumberagung and Public Elementary School 2 Margototo to obtain information regarding the use of media in the learning process inside and outside the classroom. The next stage is observation, observation activities are carried out by directly observing the learning process in the classroom, one of the functions of observation is to strengthen the analysis that will be carried out.

After collecting data through questionnaires, interviews and supported by observation, the data was analyzed using the Miles & Huberman model in Rismawati & Giyartini (2022) as follows: 1) Data reduction, namely the process of researchers grouping data that is considered important. 2) data presentation is the process of researchers in compiling information in the form of paragraphs. 3) drawing conclusions/verification, namely the process of reviewing the results of the writing to get conclusions.

DISCUSSION

The first step in obtaining data in this study is to make observations. Observation is a data collection technique by observing directly or indirectly about the things that are observed and recording them on an observation tool (Sanjaya, 2013). The observation results show that in the learning process students are classified as low in creative thinking skills, this is evidenced by the many students who are still silent and only accept the material provided by the teacher. Students are still relatively low in communicating with teachers, students look confused when the teacher asks questions about the material presented. Students tend to be busy with their own activities, less focused on listening to the teacher's explanation and students are less active in learning. Seeing these problems, it is necessary to use media or learning tools that function to facilitate the learning process (Kosasih, 2014).

Interviews were conducted with Fiki Lisnawati (2022) as the homeroom teacher for class V of public elementary school 1 Sumberagung, Nurma Yunita, class V guardian of Margototo 2 state elementary school and Ratnawati, teacher of class V, Sumberagung 2 state elementary school, Metro Kibang District, East Lampung Regency. The curriculum used in the three schools is the 2013 curriculum, educators use textbooks as learning resources in learning. This causes learning to be passive and has an impact on students' creative thinking. The media used is media that is only provided from schools such as globes and maps. The need for new media innovations to support the learning process because media is one of the solutions used as a tool so that students can be excited and understand learning easily. One of the media that can be used to support learning is KOKAMI media (mysterious card box). According to Rahmawati & Kurniawan (2017) there is a significant influence by using Kokami media when teaching and learning activities.

The results of the research were obtained based on the distribution of questionnaires regarding the use of media in thematic learning which was given to 59 students of class V elementary school 1 Sumberagung, public elementary school 2 Sumberagung, public elementary school 2 Margototo Metro Kibang East Lampung needs analysis was carried out to find out and describe the use of media one of them is the use of KOKAMI (mysterious card box) media. The following are related questionnaire results, including:

Table I. The results of distributing thematic learning attractiveness questionnaires

No	Information	The number of students			Amount	percentage
		SD 1 SA	SD 2 SA	SD 2 MGTT		
1	Very Interesting	0	0	0	0	0%
2	Interesting	4	3	2	9	15%
3	Less attractive	15	15	13	43	73%
4	Not attractive	3	3	1	7	12%
Amount		22	21	16	59	100%

Source: Results of research data processing

Table II. Results of distributing questionnaires on learning resources in thematic learning

No	Information	The number of students			Amount	percentage
		SD 1 SA	SD 2 SA	SD 2 MGTT		
1	Printed book	20	15	16	51	86%
2	Module	0	0	0	0	0%
3	LKS	2	6	0	8	14%
4	Ppts or Videos	0	0	0	0	0%
Amount		22	21	16	59	100%

Source: Results of research data processing

Table III. The results of the distribution of pleasure questionnaires for students learning to use the media

No	Information	The number of students			Amount	percentage
		SD 1 SA	SD 2 SA	SD 2 MGTT		
1	Very happy	19	13	4	36	61%
2	Happy	3	7	10	20	34%
3	Not happy	0	1	2	3	5%
Amount		22	21	16	59	100%

Source: Results of research data processing

Table IV. Results of distributing questionnaires regarding the use of mysterious card box media

No	Information	The number of students			Amount	percentage
		SD 1 SA	SD 2 SA	SD 2 MGTT		
1	Once	0	0	0	0	0%
2	Never	22	21	16	59	100%
Amount		22	21	16	59	100%

Source: Results of research data processing

Table V. The results of distributing the learning consent questionnaire using a mysterious card box

No	Information	The number of students			Amount	percentage
		SD 1 SA	SD 2 SA	SD 2 MGTT		
1	Sangat Setuju	20	15	13	48	81%
2	Setuju	2	6	3	11	19%
3	Tidak Setuju	0	0	0	0	0%
Amount		22	21	16	59	100%

Source: Results of research data processing

The table above shows the results of the questionnaire that 73% of the learning done by the teacher is less interesting. 86% of students think that the learning resources commonly used by teachers are printed books. 61% of the 59 students enjoy learning to use media in thematic learning. 81% of students agree with the use of KOKAMI media (mysterious card box) as a tool or support that can be developed as a medium in thematic learning. These things can result in decreased enthusiasm, motivation and decreased students' thinking skills. These reasons make teachers feel that the use of KOKAMI media (mysterious card boxes) in thematic learning can make learning more varied, so as to foster students' creative thinking skills. Thinking as a person's mental ability can be divided into several types, including logical, analytical, systematic, critical, and creative thinking (Siswono, 2016).

Creative Thinking is the activity of thinking to produce something creative and original. Aryana in Febrianti (2016) suggests creative thinking, namely (1) fluent, is the ability to generate many ideas, (2) flexible, is the ability to produce varied ideas, (3) original, is the ability to produce new ideas or ideas that were not previously exists, and (4) detailing, is the ability to develop or add ideas so that detailed or detailed ideas are produced. It is that creative thinking has several indicators to generate new ideas. Creative thinking can produce quality thoughts. This technology-based model also develops creative thinking skills, especially fluency and flexibility, and develops critical thinking and constructive criticism skills (Tabieh et al., 2020).

Based on the problems described, it is necessary to improve and modify classroom learning. One way to improve the learning conditions is to utilize or develop a learning media. The media is expected to be able to change and foster a new learning atmosphere so as to get a positive response from students. According to Kadir in Russiana (2014) KOKAMI (mystery boxes and cards) is a type of media combined with language games. This game is an alternative, which can be used to foster students' enthusiasm and creative

thinking. Kokami consists of a box in which there are various message cards. The message can be in the form of an order, a question or a statement written on a piece of paper that is put in a sealed envelope.

The explanation above provides an understanding that learning media has an important role in the learning process to achieve learning objectives. Creative thinking skills can be seen in the use of the media used. Why creative thinking because in 21st century school learning, educators and students must change learning patterns to become more meaningful. Improving the creative thinking of teachers or educators can utilize media that is able to represent the learning objectives to be achieved and foster students' skills that can be formed after using the media. One alternative that can be used is using KOKAMI Media (mysterious card box), this media is game-based so that students feel comfortable, excited, very enthusiastic and competitive and hone students' creative thinking abilities in learning.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of this study, it shows that learning media has an important role in the learning process, the media has a very significant role in achieving learning objectives. KOKAMI (mysterious card box) is one of the media that can be used to find out students' creative thinking skills in thematic learning. KOKAMI (mysterious card box) is an alternative media that can be used in the learning process. Teachers are expected to be more innovative in using media in learning. By using media, it is easier for teachers to practice thinking skills that must be mastered by students. Exploring the entire potential of students is an obligation for a teacher. Empowering and cultivating students' creative thinking abilities can help in achieving more meaningful learning.

REFERENCES

1. A.S Tabieh, A., M.Al-Hileh, M., M.J. Abu Afifa, H., & Yacoub Abuzagha, H. (2020). European Journal of Educational Research. *European Journal Of Educational Research*, 10(1), 13–21. <https://doi.org/10.12973/eu-jer.10.1.13>
2. Alfiyah, S., Sunyono, & Andra, D. (2023). Development of Quizz-Based Creative Thinking Skill Assessment in Thematic Learning of Elementary School Class V Students. *International Journal of Current Science Research and Review*, 06(06), 3080–3090. <https://doi.org/10.47191/ijcsrr/V6-i6-01>
3. Cetinkaya, C. (2014). The effect of gifted students ' creative problem solving program on creative thinking. *Procedia Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 116(1974), 3722–3726. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2014.01.830>
4. Chrysti Suryandari, K., Rokhmaniyah, & Wahyudi. (2021). European Journal of Educational Research. *European Journal Of Educational Research*, 10(3), 1329–1340.
5. Faturrahman, L. Y., Ermiana, I., & Khair, B. N. (2021). Pengembangan Media Kokami Pada Pembelajaran Tematik Di Kelas V Sekolah Dasar Kecamatan Pemenang. *Progres Pendidikan*, 2(1), 55–63.
6. Fauzi, I. S., Rukayah, & Budiharto, T. (2021). Pelaksanaan pembelajaran tematik pada pembelajaran jarak jauh di kelas v sekolah dasar. *Jurnal Pendidikan Ilmiah*, 7(2), 92–96.
7. Febrianti, Y., Djahir, Y., & Fatimah, S. (2016). Analisis Kemampuan Berfikir Kreatif Peserta Didik Dengan Memanfaatkan Lingkungan Pada Mata Pelajaran Ekonomi Di SMA Negeri 6 Palembang. *Jurnal Profit*, 3.
8. Hartadiyati, E., Utami, R. E., & Rubowo, M. R. (2015). Pengembangan Media Pembelajaran Puzzle Card Untuk Meningkatkan Kemampuan Berpikir Kreatif Siswa. *Seminar Nasional Pendidikan Sains V, November*, 30–34.
9. Jeet, G., & Pant, S. Creating Joyful Experiences for Enhancing Meaningful Learning and Integrating 21st Century Skills. *International Journal of Current Science Research and Review*, 6(2), 900-903
10. Kosasih, E. (2014). *Strategi Belajar dan Pembelajaran Implementasi Kurikulum 2013* (Y. Mulyadi (ed.)). YRAMA WIDYA.
11. Kurniawan, D. (2017). *Pembelajaran Terpadu Tematik (Teori, Praktik dan Penilaian)*. Alfabeta.
12. Mardiyanti, A. S. (2020). Analisis kemampuan berpikir kritis dan kreatif dalam pemecahan masalah matematika berdasarkan kemampuan matematika siswa. *EKSPOSE: Jurnal Penelitian Hukum Dan Pendidikan*, 19(1), 939–946.
13. Nuralisa, S. F., Vitasari, M., & Nestiadi, A. (2021). Pengembangan Media Pembelajaran Kokami (Kotak Kartu Misterius) Tema Pelestarian Lingkungan Untuk Meningkatkan Hasil Belajar Kognitif. *Jurnal Inovasi Pendidikan Sains*, 12(1), 33–48.
14. Permana, E. P. (2018). Pengaruh Media Sosial sebagai Sumber Belajar IPS Terhadap Motivasi Belajar, Kemampuan Berpikir Kritis dan Berpikir Kreatif Siswa Sekolah Dasar. *PINUS*, 4(1).

15. Rahmawati, A. M., & Kurniawan, R. Y. (2017). Analisis Hasil pengembangan Media KOKAMI (Kotak dan Kartu Misterius) Untuk Meningkatkan Keterampilan Berpikir Kritis , Aktivitas Belajar Dan Ketuntasan Belajar SMP-SMA. *Unesa Edisi Yudisium*, 5.
16. Rahmawati, A., Pina, E. Al, Setiono, P., Yuliantini, N., & Wurjinem. (2021). Kesulitan Guru Dalam Pembelajaran Tematik Di Kelas V Sd Negeri 38 Kota Bengkulu Selama Pembelajaran Daring. *Elementary School*, 8, 303–309.
17. Rismawati, M., & Giyartini, R. (2022). Analisis Kebutuhan Pengembangan Media Komik Matematika pada Materi Pecahan Sederhana. 9(2), 410–421.
18. Rusiana, Y. (2014). Penggunaan Media Kokami Pada Mata Pelajaran Ipa Untuk Meningkatkan Hasil Belajar Siswa Kelas Va Sdn Darungan 01 Kecamatan Tanggul Kabupaten Jember. *Pancaran*, 3(4).
19. Rusman. (2012). *Model-Model Pembelajaran*. PT Rajagrafindo Persada.
20. Sanjaya, W. (2013). *Penelitian Pendidikan Jenis, Metode dan Prosedur*. Kencana Prenanda Media Group.
21. Siswanto, R. D., & Ratiningsih, R. P. (2020). Korelasi Kemampuan Berpikir Kritis dan Kreatif Matematis Kemampuan Pemecahan Masalah Matematis Materi Bangun Ruang dengan. *ANARGYA : Jurnal Ilmiah Pendidikan Matematika*, 3(2), 96–103.
22. Siswono, T. Y. E. (2016). Berpikir Kritis dan Berpikir Kreatif sebagai Fokus Pembelajaran Matematika. *Seminar Nasional Matematika Dan Pendidikan Matematika FPMIPATI-Universitas PGRI Semarang*.
23. Wiana, W. (2018). Interactive Multimedia-Based Animation : A Study of Effectiveness on Fashion Design Technology Learning. *The Electrochemical Society*, 953. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/953/1/012024>
24. Widodo, P. E. K., & Suprayitno. (2017). Pengaruh Media Kokami Terhadap Hasil Belajar Ips Siswa Kelas V SDN Sambibulu Sidoarjo. *JPGSD*, 5(3), 1075–1084.

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